

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF MULTICAST PROTOCOLS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we report an analytic comparison of control bandwidth overheads (CBOs) for different implementations of protocol independent multicast (PIM) variants in a hierarchical network environment using combinatorial technique. We find that over networks with several numbers of hierarchies PIM variants can have significantly different CBO per group member. In particular, the modified dense mode (DM) with state refresh (DMSR) typically has significantly lower CBO per group member than DM with flood and prune (DMFP) mechanism. Also studied is the precise measure of the relative performance between sparse mode (SM) and source specific multicast (SSM) protocols. The results show that the overhead costs of these protocols depend strongly on the choice of the protocol and the operating conditions present. Our findings show that at low network utilisation (i.e., a sparse network) there is a great sensitivity as SM is by far the most efficient protocol. The performance difference between SSM and DMSR protocols is also significant as SSM is better than DMSR for small groups while for large groups DMSR is superior. These results provide useful information to the network community, particularly network designers, integrators and users.

Keywords: Control bandwidth overhead, Hierarchical networks, Multicast, Sensitivity, Network utilisation.

INTRODUCTION

Multicasting has made group communication easier and cheaper. Such communications include Internet TV, teleconferencing, video on demand, etc. In these group communications, the quality of data sent can be enhanced if the cost of the real-data and cost of constructing and maintaining their distribution trees is studied and characterized such that the control bandwidth utilized does not overwhelm and slow down the network. Apart from sparse mode and dense mode (Fenner, Handley, Holbrook et al., 2006) other multicast protocols e.g., pragmatic general multicast (PGM) (Speakman, Crowcroft, Gemmell et al., 2001) and reliable multicast transport (RMT) (Kermode and Vicisano, 2002), the modified dense mode have emerged. Out of these multicast routing protocols which run on the existing IP (Internet Protocol) with unicast infrastructure, the sparse mode has wide implementation. What follows is the quantitative characterization of the sparse mode and other protocol independent multicast (PIM) variants. The sparse mode (SM) (Fenner et al., 2006) of PIM is a form of any source multicast (ASM) (Bhattacharyya, 2003; Thaler, Fenner, and Quinn, 2004) which is characterised by a Rendezvous Point (RP), (not necessarily the data source) from which data is multicast to group members. For example, in Figure 1, of N leaf routers of stub LANs labelled $IG_0, IG_1, \dots, IG_{N-1}$, let a subset $(IG_0, IG_8, IG_{14}, IG_{15})$ with multicast group address G receive data from a source linked to MI_0 router with unicast address U via RP (RP is the root of the tree). To set up a multicast session, an application data packet ('data' in this case refers

to application data) is sent from MI_0 router. Then group members which are interested in receiving data from the data source through MI_0 router would send IGMP (Internet Group Management Protocol) control packets towards RP (or MI_0) to join the multicast group, with the join requests of IG_{14} , and IG_{15} merged by OG_2 router. Thus, if the size of a data packet is D and that of an IGMP control packet is C , then the control cost for forming G , assuming the (unique) reverse path forwarding (RPF) (Adams, Nicholas and Siadak, 2005) tree is $7C$ byte-links. In this analysis we assume that node responses are not delayed and the maximum amount of merging possible actually takes place and that groups are static. In practice this means that all round-trip times need to be less than the inter-packet arrival times, an assumption that is reasonable in the case of video of typical rates distributed with typical IP sizes of 500 - 1500 bytes, which is typically larger than a control message of at least 24 bytes. It is possible to relax one or more of these assumptions.

RP: Rendezvous Point, BSR: Bootstrap Router, DR: Designated Router ($IG_{1,,}, IG_n$) SR: Source Router

Figure 1: Three-level hypothetical hierarchical network architecture, data source outside the Network.

Source Specific Multicast (SSM) protocol is a variant of SM (Holbrook and Cain, 2006). It uses IGMP version 3 (IGMPv3) (Holbrook, Cain, and Haberman, 2006; Cain, Deering, Kouvelas, Fenner et al., 2002) to construct and update its delivery data path tree. In the case of our running example, MI_0 router would flood the network with (U, G) 'channels' using IGMP control message. When the control message is received, $IG_0, IG_1 \dots IG_{N-1}$ routers would determine channels for which they have interested hosts. Subscriptions then travel hop-by-hop towards MI_0 router for the group and in each router a subscription passes through, multicast tree state for group G is instantiated (Fenner, et al., 2006). In our example, the control cost of G is seen to be $35C + 7C = 42C$ byte-link (i.e., the $35C$ byte-link is due to flooding, while $7C$ byte-link is the responses of group members IG_0, IG_8, IG_{14} , and IG_{15}).

Dense mode with flood and prune (DMFP) protocol (Adam et al., 2005) uses a flood and prune mechanism to create and update its delivery data path tree. It assumes that when a source starts sending data packets, downstream systems would want to receive the multicast datagram. Therefore, at time $t=0$, MI_0 router floods the entire network with a data packet and any router (i.e., $IG_0, IG_1, \dots, IG_{N-1}$) that has no interest in receiving data packet from the source will prune itself out of the group by sending a prune (control) message to upstream routers. In the running example, OG_3 and OG_4 routers have no interested downstream routers; therefore the data packets received by these routers as a result of flooding are unwanted. Thus, the control cost of group G is $28(D+C)$ byte-link since a wanted data packet is not a control overhead. Flooding and pruning is repeated every T_{FP} seconds.

Dense mode with state refresh (DMSR) protocol (Adams et al., 2005) introduces a state refresh mechanism to maintain its delivery data path tree, G . At $t=0$, initial flooding of a data packet occurs and a corresponding pruning takes place. Thereafter, at every T_{SR} seconds a state refresh message of size C is sent by MI_0 router and the message is propagated throughout the network. When received by $IG_0, IG_1 \dots IG_{N-1}$ routers, the state refresh message causes existing prune states to stay pruned. Thus, for group G the CBO costs for both DMSR and DMFP protocols are the same because of the initial flooding and pruning operation. The benefit of DMSR protocol is seen for $t>0$, that is, when DMSR protocol uses control messages instead of data packets to maintain (or update) its delivery data path tree.

From the above examples, DMSR protocol is likely to have a lower CBO per group member than DMFP protocol for small groups as DMSR uses control messages to update its delivery data path tree whereas DMFP uses data packets. However, for very large groups DMFP protocol can be superior to DMSR protocol since the data in the data packets used as control messages are not wasted. Also we might like to have a precise measure of the relative performance of SM and SSM protocols. In what follows, a quantitative comparison is made between the above described PIM variants, taking into account all possible multicast groups in a network of the form in Figure

NETWORK SPECIFICATION

We choose to compare the PIM protocols in strictly hierarchical network topology as shown in Fig 1. The network topology is a representative of a three-layer hierarchy often found in the Internet. The motivation for using hierarchical networks in our analytical investigations is that they do not only help to simplify computations, but also allow a lot of analytical calculations to be done. Further motivations for the use of hierarchical networks for analytical investigations are given in (Sun, Trappe and Liu, 2004; Kaur, and Sachdeva, 2012; Mir, Musa, Torresand and Swamy, 2014; Miegham and Janic, 2002).

Figure 1 corresponds to an IP backbone, which is represented by router MI_0 (MI_0 is used as RP router by SM protocol). Internet Service Providers (ISPs) are represented by $GO_0, GO_1, GO_2, GO_3,$ and GO_4 , and organisation sites (e.g., organisation LANs), are represented by $IG_0 \dots IG_{N-1}$ (in this example, the number of sub LAN routers is 30, i.e., $N=30$).

MULTICAST GROUP SPECIFICATION

The set of all possible multicast groups formed from N leaf routers at the bottom of the hierarchy is called the power set of the set of routers. There is isomorphism between the power set and the N -bit binary number, which represents a multicast group. The relationship between the power set of the set of group members and an N -bit binary number specifies the multicast group identity. That is, a multicast group is specified by the binary numbers of 0 and 1. For example, if a multicast group of size S is given, then we obtain its restrictive

partitions (Zoghbi and Stojmenovic, 2004) such that none of the parent routers (immediate routers above the leaf routers) has more than n (where n is the number of possible downstream active leaf routers of a parent router) leaf routers. Then, each number in a partition is converted to a binary number, where binary number 1 represents an active group member in a parent router. This follows that the binary number 0 shows that a particular leaf router is not an active group member. Hence the power set of the set of multicast groups for a given network is 2^N .

Following from Figure 1, there are five parent routers represented by $GO_0, GO_1, GO_2, GO_3,$ and GO_4 , and each has six leaf routers. Hence the three level network in Figure 1 is specified as $N(5,6)$ and the leaf routers are represented by a 30-bit binary number. Therefore the number of multicast groups in this network is 2^{30} . The number of groups with size 16 is computed as ${}^{30}C_{16}$ and one way to represent this group is 010111001000001111100001111101.

COST METRIC

We evaluate the overheads of the protocols in terms of control bandwidth overhead (CBO) consumed to construct and maintain the distribution trees of multicast groups in the network. In both sparse and dense modes operations in typical hierarchical networks, the overhead varies more quickly than the actual data costs for different groups. Hence we choose to use CBO cost metric, assuming the links are symmetrical, in estimating the impact of the protocols in terms of the number of links traversed by a packet. Besides this, our choice of CBO cost metric may be appropriate in case of large networks where the group may be very large and hence the control costs, but data exchanges are small and relatively infrequent. Further motivations for the use of CBO as cost metric are given in (Wei and Estrin, 1995; Chen and Ashakkumar, 2013).

COST MODEL

We choose our metric for the PIM comparison to be the mean CBO per group member averaged (with respect to an appropriate probability measure) over 2^N multicast groups in a network. In this paper, we assume a homogeneous network and the probability of a particular group occurring is a function of its size, $P(S)$. From the earlier examples, the CBO cost of a given group is a function of the restricted partition of S (i.e., $C=C(\{s_i\})$) and the unique decomposition of $S=\sum_{i=0}^n is_i$ (where s_i is the number of OG routers with i downstream leaf routers, and the number of OG routers in a network is denoted by m). Therefore, the number of groups with respect to the restricted partition $\{s_i\}$ in a network is given by the multinomial factor,

$$Q(\{S\}) = \sum_{S=\sum_{i=1}^n is_i} \frac{m!}{s_0!+s_1!+\dots+s_n!} \prod_{i=0}^n \binom{n}{i} s_i \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

If we assume that a leaf router (i.e., a sub LAN) is a member of a group with probability p (and q is the probability that a leaf router is not a member of a group), then $P(S)$ is a Binomial distribution,

$$P(S) = p^S q^{N-S} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

We obtain the weighted average overhead cost by summing over the probability distribution of multicast groups as,

$$\frac{AvCBO_p}{\dots\dots\dots} = \frac{\sum_{S=0}^N P(S) \sum_{S=\sum_{i=0}^n is_i} Q(\{S.\}) C(\{S.\})}{\sum_{S=0}^N P(S) \sum_{S=\sum_{i=0}^n is_i} Q(\{S.\})} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where $C(\{S.\})$ of DMFP, is specified as,

$$C(\{S.\})_{dmfp} = \left((D + C) \sum_{j=0}^n s_j + a_j \right) \times t \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where a_j is the number of links that connect a branch router with s_j leaf routers to the IP backbone router and t is time measured in minutes. The analysis of multicast groups for source inside the networks is more involved and will be presented in an expanded work. We obtain the analytic results for three and higher level networks by using the cost model in (3) iteratively (e.g., a four level network can be partitioned into a number of three level networks).

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Shown in Figure 2 is the computed results from model (3) for three and four level networks with parent-child cardinalities specification $N(5,10)$ and $N(6,2,5)$ respectively, $C=40$ bytes and $D=1500$ bytes for the PIM variants - SM, DMFP, DMSR, and SSM protocols. Comparing the performance of these protocols in these two different networks we find that the control costs are relatively highly sensitive to the number of network hierarchical layers in case of SM protocol. The lack of sensitivity of DMFP and DMSR protocols is because there are some groups with very large control costs - namely sparse groups (with large diameter) which involve a lot of pruning cost. However, there are not very many of these groups so they do not have significant effect (or contribution) on the average. In a typical multicast group, the control costs are obtained from the lowest levels of the hierarchy and as the network hierarchy grows it becomes increasingly likely that an internal node will have a downstream group member, hence that node will not send any further prune messages upstream. Even if there are a several number of levels (or hierarchies) most will not contribute to the control costs. Indeed it may be possible (e.g., for a large group size) that above a certain level there is zero probability that there is a downstream router that is not a member of the distribution tree. The probability that a given router at a particular level i in an L level network has no member downstream given that the group size is S is,

$$p(S, n, \dots, n_{i+1}, \dots, n_L, i) = \frac{\binom{N-X}{s}}{\binom{N}{s}} \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Where n_i is the number of downstream routers of a parent (or upstream) router at level i and

$$X = n_i \times n_{i+1} \times \dots \times n_L \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

As long as $S \leq (N - X)$ and zero otherwise. As both the network hierarchy and the mean group size increase, DMSR protocol becomes superior to SM and SSM protocols. The reason for this behaviour is that SM and SSM protocols require join messages that need to propagate to the root of the tree hence the control costs of SM and SSM protocols grow with the numbers of hierarchies and group sizes. If the administration is such that a given amount of bandwidth is allocated to control cost, then the relative costs give the relative frequencies with which the distribution trees of the protocols are refreshed. Comparing DMSR and DMFP protocols, the former will be more responsive to new group members. This method can be used to determine flood, join/prune or state refresh intervals which are usually given as ad hoc defaults in Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) documents.

Figure 2: Cost performance of the PIM protocols in different network hierarchies: SM-L3, DMFP-L3, DMSR-L3, and SSM-L3 are results of three level networks, while SM-L4, DMFP-L4, DMSR-L4, and SSM-L4 are graphs of four level network results.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we compare the relative performance of PIM variants in strictly hierarchical networks using combinatorial technique. We confirm our results with that of exhaustive enumeration technique. The results show that the overhead cost does depend strongly on the choice of the protocol and the operating conditions present. At low network utilisation (i.e., a sparse network) there is a great sensitivity as SM is by far the most efficient protocol. The performance difference between SSM and DMSR protocols is very significant as SSM is better than DMSR for small groups while for large groups DMSR is superior (see Figure 2). Compare with other protocols, DMFP is seen to be very inefficient as the name suggests. However, as the mean group size of the network increases the difference between protocols narrow considerably as shown in Figure 2. Our numerical investigation confirms that the overhead is a sensitive function of the protocols chosen and the mean group size of the network.

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